

KNOWLEDGE OF HIV/AIDS AND SEXUAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PORT-HARCOURT
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the knowledge of HIV/AIDS and sexual behaviours of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. A two- staged random sampling techniques was used to select Four hundred students. Data was collected using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square statistics at 0.05 significant levels. The mean age of respondents was 16.3±1.6years, 68.7% were females, 31.3% were males, and 99.5% were Christians. Overall mean knowledge score was 15.9±3.6. About half (51.0%) of the respondents had knowledge score greater than 50%. The study revealed a non-significant relationship between gender and knowledge of HIV/AIDS. However more (64.8%) females compared to (35.2%) males had good knowledge of HIV/AIDS. More than a quarter (28.9%) of the respondents had sexual partners. Out of this, 39.4% did not use any form of protection during last sexual episode and mean age at sexual debut was 14.2±3.3years. The mean number of sexual partners was 1.5±1.1partners. Knowledge of HIV/AIDS was high while risky sexual behaviour persists. Behavioural change intervention including sex education among secondary students is therefore recommended.

KEYWORDS: knowledge, HIV/AIDS, sexual behaviour, secondary school.

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INTRODUCTION

Human Immunodeficiency Virus and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV and AIDS) are one of the greatest unresolved challenges threatening human development. The epidemic continues to be a major public health threat in many countries of the world with 95% of such cases in developing countries (UNAIDS, 2006). AIDS represent the advanced and final stage of HIV infection during which the HIV infected individual's immune system is depleted to the extent that it would be not be able to fight simple infections most healthy people can resist called "opportunistic infections"(UNAIDS/WHO, 2001). Globally, the 2009 Joint United Nations Programme on AIDS report revealed that 60 million people have been infected, with some 25 million deaths and 14 million orphaned children in Southern Africa, since the epidemic began (UNAIDS, 2009). Nigeria with an estimated population of over 160 million ([CIA World Factbook](#), 2012) recorded her first case of AIDS in 1986 (Saad, 2008), since then the epidemic has steadily increased due to the low literacy level, high poverty level and poor health seeking behaviour as well as the limited access to health services and low socio-economic status of women in the society. (Saad, 2008). The 2008 sentinel survey in Nigeria revealed that about 3.4million people living with the AIDS virus with 3.3% prevalence rate for adolescents. Rivers State Nigeria has a prevalence rate of 7.3% and was targeted as one of the high prevalent areas in Nigeria (United Nations General Assembly Special Session (UNGASS), 2010).

The awareness of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria is high cutting across the different strata of the society. Studies have shown that young people and adolescents in Nigeria have good knowledge of route of transmission of

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HIV/AIDS. These include sexual intercourse (Isiugo-Abanihe, 1994; Oladepo & Brieger, 1994; Unuigbo and Ogbeide, 1999 and Omoteso, 2004; Ruma, 2009; Ugboma, Koffreh and Nwauche, 2010; Ajayi and Omotayo, 2010); Mother-to-child transmission (MTCT) (Bassey, Abasiubong, Ekanem, and Abasiatan, (2009); unscreened blood transfusion (Nwokocha and Nwakoby, 2000; Smith, 2003; Ajila, *et al.*, 2006 and Ruma 2009); sharing of contaminate sharp skin piercing object (Ajila, *et al.*, 2006; Ruma, 2009 and Bassey, *et al.*, 2009); consistent and rightful use of condom (FMOH, 2005; NCP, 2009; Tung, *et al.*, 2008; , Bassey, *et al.*, 2009; Ruma 2009); Abstinence (Smith, 2003; Bassey, *et al.*, 2009)

Knowledge plays a role as a predictor of HIV risk behaviour and remains the key modifiable factor (Osborne, Paasche-Orlow, Davis and Wolf, 2007; Baptiste, Voisin, Smithgall, Martinez and Henderson, 2007). Knowledge of HIV-related issues has been shown to be associated with delayed sexual debut and consistent use of condom and reduction in the number of sexual partners (Jackson, 2002). Initiation of sexual activity before marriage is frequent in many Africa countries including Nigeria. For many young people in Sub-Saharan Africa, as in much of the rest of the world, adolescence marks the entry into sexual activity (Prata *et al.*, 2005).The sexual habits formed during adolescence are often continued into adulthood (Rwenge 2000; Prata *et al.*, 2005), and as such the adolescent period marks an opportune time for behavioural change interventions.

Though this generation of young people is been refer to as AIDS generation (Kiragu, 2001) yet studies have shown that age at sexual debut (first sexual intercourse) had decreased despite the HIV scourge in Nigeria and more especially the impart on young people. The 2008 National Demographic Health Survey in Nigeria (NPC, 2008) indicated that 16% of adolescent girls had their sexual debut by age 15years. A higher prevalence was recorded in a study in Niger state in 2003 where 32.7% of the study population ages 11-14years were sexually active (Sunmola, Dipeolu, Babalola and Adebayo, 2003). A study in South-Eastern State (Enugu) of Nigeria among junior secondary school students revealed that 45.8% were sexually active with 89.3% of those sexually active having sexual debut between ages 11-14years (Nwaorgu, Onyenko, Okolo, Obadike and Enibe, 2008). Also, studies by MacPhail and Campbell (2001) and Kapiga and Lugalla (2002) have shown that many young people who commence sexual relations do not take preventive measures to avoid infection, thereby exposing themselves to the risk of infection with STIs. In their own study, Singh and Bankole provide evidence that the practice of sexual intercourse with multiple partners is widespread among young people aged 15-19 in sub-Saharan Africa with quite a substantial number of women reported having two or more partners (Singh & Bankole,2001). The recent study of Imaledo, Peter-Kio and Asuoquo (2012) showed that 30.4% of the study respondents had their sexual debut between age 10-19years.Though available records shows wide spread of awareness and increased knowledge of the epidemiology of HIV/AIDS, many do not practice what they know. It reaffirmed the assertion that increased knowledge of HIV/AIDS does not always result in a positive behavioural change (CDC, 1995). Hence the need to put in place behavioural changes intervention targeting young people most especially in sub-Saharan Africa.

Researchers have identified use of condom as one of the means of protection against contracting the disease but recent studies in some countries in Sub-Saharan Africa have shown that contraceptive use is low in these countries including Nigeria (NPC, 2009; Kapiga and Lugalla 2002; Maswanya, Moji, Horiguchi, Nagata, Aoyagi, Honda and Takemoto,1999; Toure, Koffi, Kouassi-Gohou, Kokoun, Angbo-Effi, Koffi and Diarra-Nam,2005; Nworgu, *et al.*, 2008; Durojaiye, 2011; [Maswanya](#), [Moji](#), [Horiguchi](#) & [Nagata](#), 1998)

Many studies have been conducted in the past on impact of knowledge on sexual behaviour among vulnerable group especially adolescent but few studies have an in-depth looked at knowledge of HIV/AIDS and sexual behaviour of adolescents in secondary school students in Rivers State of recent. This study therefore assessed the knowledge of HIV/AIDS and sexual behaviour of students in selected senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Setting

There are two-hundred and forty-five (255) owned government senior secondary schools in Rivers state. Out of which eleven are in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area (PHALGA) (two boys (single) schools, three girls (single) schools and six co-educational senior secondary schools). Three schools one each were selected from the three categories (boys(single) girls (single) and co-educational). The schools selected for the study were Enitonia high School, Government Girls Secondary School Oromineke, and Community Secondary School Abuloma, Port Harcourt. Enitona High School Borokiri Port Harcourt, boys only secondary school located at Borokiri area of Port Harcourt was founded by Reverend Potts Johnson in 1932 and currently has a population of five hundred and thirty students (530).Government Girls secondary school Oromineke was founded during Governor Oyakilomeh's regime in 1985. It is located at Wogu street D/Line in Port Harcourt and currently has students population of one thousand, six hundred and sixty-six students (1,666) while Community Secondary School Abuloma is located at Trans-Amadi area It was founded in 1991, presently has a total number of five hundred and seventy two(572) students. The three schools had a total population of two thousand and seven hundred and seventy-eight (2,768) students at the time of the study (Post-primary schools board, 2012).

Population of the study

The study population consisted of all students of the selected Senior Secondary Schools (SSS) in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area.

Study design

The study employed a descriptive cross –sectional survey design where knowledge on signs and symptoms, mode of transmission, preventive measures, causative agent of HIV/AIDS and Sexual behaviour of senior secondary school students in PHALGA were explored

Sample and sampling techniques

A two stage random sampling techniques was adopted for the study

Stage 1: Simple random sampling was used to select three (3) senior secondary schools

Stage 2: stratified (proportionate) random sampling were adopted to select 400 respondents from each of the strata (senior secondary schools)

Instrument for data collection

A pre-tested self-administered semi structured questionnaire containing 23-point knowledge questions and questions on sexual behaviour of students was used for data collection. Section A consisted mainly on questions on socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Section B asked questions on awareness and knowledge of HIV/AIDS and Section C explored students sexual behaviour.

Data analysis

Each interview started with an introduction and overview of the research including the objectives of the study. The respondents were told not to write any name on the self-administered questionnaire. Respondents were encouraged to ask questions on what they do not understand in the questionnaire. Explanations were given to respondents as required to aid their understanding of unfamiliar terms. The questionnaires were retrieved back from each respondent immediately after completion and they were reviewed for completeness.

Data Management, Analysis and Presentation

Administered copies of the questionnaire were edited and coded with the aid of a coding guide. Coded data were entered into a computer for analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 15.0. In assessing knowledge level, every correct response was scored 1 and a wrong response was scored zero. These scores were pooled together to get a three-range level of knowledge. Those who scored between 0 - 6 points were categorized as having poor knowledge, those who scored 7–16 points were categorized to have an average level of knowledge and those with 17-23 points had good knowledge of HIV/AIDS. Frequency counts were

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carried out on all the variables while continuous categorical variables were analyzed using ANOVA at 0.05 significant level.

RESULTS

More of the respondents (52.9%) were in Senior Secondary class 2. Majority (68.7%) were females, 85.3% were between the ages 15 and 19, and 12.1% were aged 10-14years with a mean age of 16.3 ± 1.6 years. Virtually all (99.5%) were Christians (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
School		
Enitonia High School	76	19.0
GGSS Oromineke	240	60.2
CSS Abuloma	83	20.8
Total	399	100.0
Class of study		
SS1	188	47.1
SS2	211	52.9
Total	399	100.0
Gender		
Male	125	31.3
Female	274	68.7
Total	399	100.0
Age*		
10-14	46	12.1
15-19	325	85.3
20-24	10	2.6
Total	381	100.0
Mean age = 16.3 ± 1.6 years		
Religion		
Christianity	397	99.5
Islam	2	0.5
Total	399	100.0

Table 2: Show respondents' awareness on HIV/AIDS. Virtually all the respondents (99.2%) were aware of HIV/AIDS. The mass media (radio/television)(97.5%) topped the list of sources of information on HIV/AIDS among respondents.

Table 2: Respondents awareness on HIV/AIDS

Awareness on HIV/AIDS	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Ever heard of HIV/AIDS		
Yes	396	99.2
No	3	0.8
Sources of information*		
Radio / television	389	97.5
Parents	340	85.2
Friends	332	83.2
Doctors / nurses	309	77.4
Internet	22	55.1
Health clubs	301	75.4
Newspaper/magazine	327	82.0
Infected person	130	32.6

* Multiple responses

Questions were asked on signs and symptoms of HIV/AIDS. More (77.1%) of the respondents agreed to unexplained weight loss ≥ 10 kg as a sign and symptom of HIV/AIDS and followed by persistent cough for more than 1 month (67.8%).

Respondents' knowledge on the mode of transmission was high as a majority (93.9%) of respondent were of the view that unprotected sexual intercourse with an infected partner can lead to the transmission of AIDS while 90.2% were of the view that one can contract the disease through sharing of sharp skin piercing objects. Incorrect knowledge of HIV/AIDS still exist as 25.5% of the study respondents were of the belief that people can contract HIV/AIDS using same toilet seat with an infected. On prevention of HIV/AIDS avoid sharing of sharp skin piercing objects topped the list of prevention followed by Abstaining from sex (91.7%) (Table 3)

The overall knowledge score of respondents were pooled on a scale of 23point. Those who scored less than seven (<7) were said to have poor knowledge, 7-16 average knowledge and those who scored 17-23 were said to have good knowledge. A little above half (51.1%) of the respondents had good knowledge of HIV/AIDS, only 2.3% had poor knowledge with a mean knowledge of 15.9 ± 3

Table 3: Respondents knowledge of HIV/AIDS

Knowledge of HIV/AIDS	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Don't know F (%)
Signs and symptoms*			
Diarrhoea for more than 1 month	171(43.3)	41(10.4)	183(46.3)
Weakness for ≥ 1 month	249(62.9)	42(10.6)	105(26.5)
Persistent cough for ≥ 1 month	268(67.8)	39(9.9)	88(22.3)
Swollen glands	164(41.7)	49(12.5)	180(45.8)
Rashes on the body	226(57.1)	64(16.2)	106(26.8)
Unexplained weight loss ≥ 10 kg	306(77.1)	16(4.0)	75(18.9)
Pneumonia	94(24.0)	57(14.5)	241(61.5)
Memory loss, depression and other neurological disorders	161(40.9)	86(21.8)	147(37.3)
Mode of transmission*			
Unprotected sexual intercourse.	372(93.9)	10(2.5)	14(3.5)
An infected mother to child.	352(88.9)	21(5.3)	23(5.8)
Transfusion of unscreened blood and its products.	331(83.8)	15(3.8)	49(12.4)
Sharing of sharp skin piercing objects.	357(90.2)	24(6.1)	15(3.8)
Using same Toilet seats.**	101(25.5)	208(52.5)	87(22.0)
Hugging an infected person.**	36(9.1)	304(77.2)	54(13.7)
Touching an infected person.**	30(7.6)	325(82.5)	39(9.9)
Prevention*			
Abstaining from sex	365(91.7)	16(4.0)	17(4.3)
Correct and consistent use of condom	294(73.9)	46(11.6)	58(14.6)
Avoid sharing of sharp skin piercing objects	372(93.5)	12(3.0)	14(3.5)
Protection from traditional healers.**	62(15.6)	253(63.7)	82(20.7)
Screening of blood/its products before use.	307(77.3)	28(7.1)	62(15.6)
Be faithful to one uninfected partner	265(66.9)	59(14.9)	72(18.2)

*Multiple responses **incorrect responses

Sexual Behaviour of Respondents

Respondents' sexual behaviour are presented in Table 7. About twenty-nine percent of the respondents had sexual partners out of which 39.4% used condom in the last 3 months preceding the study(see table 7).Also, of those who had sex, majority (91.9%) had their sexual debut between ages 10 and 19years with a mean age of 14.2±3.3 years. Majority (72.1%) had just one (1) sexual partner with mean partners of 1.5±1.1 (Table 4).

Table 4: Sexual Behaviour of Respondents

Sexual behaviour	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Have a sexual partner		
Yes	114	28.9
No	280	71.1
Total	394	100.0
Use condom*		
Yes	43	39.4
No	66	60.4
Total	109	100.0
Age at sexual debut*		
4-9	8	7.2
10-19	102	91.9
20 & above	1	0.9
Total	111	100.0
Mean age 14.2±3.3years		
No. of sex partners*		
1	75	72.1
2	14	13.5
3	8	7.7
4	3	2.9
>4	4	3.8
Total	104	100.0
Mean sexual partners 1.5±1.1 partners		

*non responses were excluded from the analysis

The result of this study shows a non-significant relationship, between socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (class, Gender, age) and knowledge. However more (54.3%) respondents in SS1 had good knowledge about HIV/AIDS compared to 48.3% of those in SSII ($p>0.05$). Again more (57.6%) of the males respondents were more knowledgeable compared to 48.2% of the female respondents ($p>0.05$). Also more (52.2%) respondents aged 10-14years were knowledgeable compared with respondents aged 16-19years (50.2%) and 20-24years (50.0%) ($p>0.05$). (Table 5)

Table 5: Relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and Knowledge of HIV/AIDS among respondents.

Socio-demographic characteristics	Knowledge			df	F	P-value
	Good(17-23) F (%)	Average(7-16) F (%)	Poor (0-6) F (%)			
Class						
SS1	102(54.3)	87(44.10)	3(1.6)	2	0.43	0.95*
SS2	102(48.3)	103(48.8)	6(2.8)			
Gender						
Male	72(57.6)	50(40.0)	3(2.4)	2	0.91	0.40*
Female	132(48.2)	136(49.6)	6(2.2)			
Age(years)						
10-14	24(52.2)	21(40.0)	1(2.2)	2	1.79	0.16*
15-19	163(50.2)	154(47.4)	8(2.5)			
20-24	5(50.0)	5(50.0)	0(0)			

*Not significant

The findings of this study show that there is no significant association between knowledge of HIV/AIDS and use of condom. However, more (58.1%) of respondents with good knowledge of HIV/AIDS used condom compared to respondents with average knowledge and poor knowledge ($p>0.05$) (Table 6).

Table 6: Relationship between knowledge of HIV/AIDS and condom use at sexual intercourse

Socio-demographic characteristics	Knowledge			Total	df	F	P-value
	Good(17-23) F (%)	Average(7-16) F (%)	Poor (0-6) F (%)				
Use of condom							
Used	25(58.1)	16(37.2)	2(4.7)	43(39.4)	2	2.10	0.127 *
Did not use	28(42.4)	37(56.1)	1(1.5)	66(60.6)			
Total	53(48.6)	53(48.6)	3(2.8)	109(100.0)			

*Not significant

DISCUSSION

The finding of the study revealed a high level of awareness of HIV/AIDS among the study population and mass media topped the list of their sources of information. This finding corroborates those of Brook (1999), Sallar (2009) and Ruma (2009), but at variance with the studies of Bekeny (2009), and Owusu (2010), where health personnel and family members topped the list of the sources of information. The technological advancement witnessed of recent in the country in the area of Information Technology (IT) may be responsible for this as most HIV/AIDS programmes in the country have taken advantage of this means to relay educative programmes on the epidemiology of the disease to the general public. Also the role of health professional who are well trained in educating young people about HIV/AIDS is necessary to increase awareness.

The finding of this study indicated good knowledge on signs and symptoms of HIV/AIDS. However respondents need to be informed that these signs and symptoms could accompany any other disease and that HIV itself does not show on the human face. Another finding of this study indicated a high level of knowledge on mode of transmission of HIV/AIDS. This finding is similar to the findings of Thomson, Currie, Todd and Elton, (1999), Savaser (2003), Ajila, Adeyemo and Owojore (2006), Ruma (2009), and Acquah and Hammond (2011) where there was a high knowledge on unprotected sexual intercourse as mode of transmission among their study population. However the finding of this study differs from the finding of Huang *et al* (2005), Ajayi and Omotayo (2010) where knowledge on sexual intercourse as a means of contracting HIV/AIDS was low. Despite the high level of knowledge on mode of transmission, some misconception about means of contracting the disease was however noticed as some respondents were still of the opinion that HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by sharing same toilet, hugging touching an infected person. There is the need for more to be done to clear these gray areas as this can lead to discrimination and stigmatization of people living HIV/AIDS among the study population.

More respondents were also knowledgeable on the mother to child transmission of HIV/AIDS (MTCT) this similar to the findings of Thomson *et al* (1999), FMOH (2005), Bassey, *et al* (2009), Tung, Ding and Farmer (2008) and Owusu (2010) where a high proportion of respondents knew of the MTCT as mode of transmission. However differs from the findings of the study of Ferrer, Cranelli, Cuzzman, Cabiesses, Irrarazabel, Bernales and Araya (2007) where less than half of the respondents knew about MTCT.

Also the findings of this study revealed that more respondents knew transfusion of unscreened blood and its products as a route of transmission of HIV/AIDS. This is similar to the findings of Thomson *et al.*, (1999), Nwokocha and Nwakoby (2000); Smith (2003); Savaser (2003); Ajila, *et al.*, (2006); Ruma (2009); and Bassey *et al.*, (2009) and at variance with the findings of Ajayi, *et al.*, (2010). The result of the study further revealed that a higher proportion (90.2%) of respondents had knowledge of sharing of sharp skin piercing objects as a route of transmission. This is similar to the findings of Gellert *et al.*, (1995), Thomson *et al.*, (1999), Nwokocha and Nwakoby (2000), Savaser (2003), Ajila *et al.*, (2006), Ruma (2009), and Bassey, *et al.*, (2009).

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The last three decades have witnessed an unprecedented effort in both human and financial resources devoted to education on the need to know the risk involve in unprotected sex and other sexual risky behaviour in order to arrest the Sexually Transmitted Infection (STI) including HIV/AIDS surge which has been ravaging Sub-Sahara Africa. Despite the fact that proper and consistent condom use was identify by the study population as one of the means of contracting HIV/AIDS yet risky sexual behavior such as unprotected sexual intercourse and multiple sexual partner was noticed among respondents in this study. This corroborate the finding of a study carried out in Tanzania and South Africa among secondary schools students which revealed that 23.4% reported being sexually active only few of them use condom (Abdool-Karim, Preston-Whyte, and Abdool-Karim, 1992; Peltzer and Promtussananon, 2005; Exavery, Lutambi, Mubyazi, Kweka, Mbaruku and Masanja, 2011; Peltzer, 2000;)

This is revealing and calls for concerted effort from stakeholders considering that these are adolescent who the future of the country are. This is because as young people become sexually active, many lack the necessary information and skills needed to have safe sex which could lead to increase in HIV infection (Kelly, 2003). There is the need to urgently intensify the introduction of sex education into the school curriculum to emphasis the risk involve in adolescent having not only sexual partners but multiple sexual partners and having unprotected sex putting them at risk of contracting STIs and unintended pregnancies which often lead to unsafe abortion and untimely death.

The age at sexual debut in this study was low; this is in agreement with previous studies where majority had their sexual debut between 10-19years (Sunmola, *et al.*, 2003; Nworgu *et al.*, 2008; Imaledo, *et al.*, 2012; Fawole, Asuzu, and Odutun, 1999). It is interesting to note that several years after the World Health Organisation (WHO) raised the alarm that at least one in five of world's female population has been physically or sexually abused and that among children, sexual abuse is increasing and the girl child is more at risk, the experience of majority of respondents in this study attest to the fact that this heinous act still persist. This may be due to the fact that men prefer young girls who are mostly tricked as sexual partners because they assume they are sexually inexperienced and as such are less likely to be infected with sexually transmitted disease (Ekwu, 1986) and the fact that the societal norms favors and shield the perpetrators from condemnation and sanctions (Fawole, Ajuwon and Osungbade, 2004).

CONCLUSION

Knowledge of HIV/AIDS was high. However, respondents in this study were sexually active and risky sexual practices were identified among the study population.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. It is important that future interventions by stakeholders in schools focus more on how to consolidate on knowledge that young people have on HIV/AIDS to translating to positive sexual behavior.
2. Government at all levels should legislate on criminalizing teen sexual abuse and provide the platform where victims of child sexual abuse can be heard and provide needed support for those who had been sexually abused.
3. Teachers being foster parents in school should also be educated on HIV/AIDS in other to educate the young people under their care as students tend to believe what is taught by their teachers.
4. There is the need to include comprehensive sexuality education in the school curriculum. This should be done in earnest since the argument against it does not remove the fact that young people are getting sexual active without proper information and education on sexuality and all it entails.

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